

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF A GREAT SCULPTURE IN SOCIETY

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Abstract... In this article, "The role of majestic sculpture in society. and importance." The types of sculpture are discussed about the creativity of sculptors and their creations.

Keywords: Majestic sculpture, relief sculpture, Shapes, light, shadow, easel sculpture, monumental, memorial (memorial) decorative sculpture, monumental, decorative sculpture.

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РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВЕЛИКОЙ СКУЛЬПТУРЫ В ОБЩЕСТВЕ

МАНОВАТЛИ НАЙКАЛТАРОШЛИКНИНГ ЖАМИЯТДА TUTGAN O'RNINI VA ANAMIYATI

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Abstract... В статье «Роль величественной скульптуры в жизни общества. и важность». Обсуждаются виды скульптуры, о творчестве скульпторов и их творениях.

Keywords: Величественная скульптура, рельефная скульптура, Формы, свет, тень, станковая скульптура, монументальная, мемориальная (мемориальная) декоративная скульптура, монументальная, декоративная скульптура..

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It is known that visual activity is mainly carried out in three types: painting, pencil drawing and sculpture. Each of them has its roots and stages of historical development. The role of the art of ancient Egypt, ancient Asia, ancient India, and China is very important in the civilization of the world. The first activities of painting and sculpture began to take shape in these centers of culture, and their laws were developed. Thus, until now, these types of art have developed in new directions and styles.

During the years of independence in our country, in addition to the reconstruction and repair of historical monuments, the initiative of erecting a number of statues in their honor in order to perpetuate the names of intelligent scientists, playwrights, labor heroes and historical figures who came out of the people was reflected in the government's decisions, and this task is being

successfully performed. This is a proof of how contemporary and folk art the sculpture type is.²¹⁶

Sculptures mainly depict human and partly animal figures. In it, a person is depicted by means of voluminous, soft - flexible, figure and spatial forms. The statue is such an object that the viewer can see it from all sides. Therefore, in sculpture, the main artistic tools are size, shadow (sluyet), weight - tone, signs of soft flexibility are placed in such a way that all its sides are visible, and the shadow is clearly embodied in space.

Sculpture is a perfect and complex type of fine art based on three-dimensional representation of existence in volumetric forms.

In fine art, the image object of this type is mainly human figure, as well as animals (animalistics), natural objects (landscape) and objects (still life) and various views are depicted in volume. There are two main forms of this art - circular sculptures that allow you to observe by turning, and a relief (bubble) image, which is intended for the observer to see only from one side. Relief sculpture, in turn, is divided into bas-relief, where the image of the object is slightly exaggerated on the surface, and gore-relief, the image of which is much more prominent than the surface. There is also another type of carved image (counter-relief) that is made on a flat surface so that it is noticeable due to the play of light.

Figure 1: Types of sculptural art

According to the function and content, sculpture is divided into the following types: monumental sculpture, decorative sculpture, machine sculpture.

²¹⁶ Izbasarov Izzatilla. "Sculpture" is a textbook for students of fine art and engineering graphics, painting (painting) and applied art (art ceramics). - Samarkand: Sam DU, 2021. p. 3.

Majestic sculpture means monumental, that is, majestic sculpture. They are installed in the square and streets for the general public.

*137-rasm. Amir Temurhaykali
Samarqand shahri (1996 y.)*

*138-rasm. Amir Temur haykali
Shahrisabz shahri (1996 y.)*

Majestic sculpture includes important historical events related to the art of architecture, monuments and sculptural ensembles erected in order to perpetuate the memory of famous people, and these have independent importance and express a great meaning in themselves.

However, this type of sculpture should be in harmony with the immediate environment, architectural structures and nature, which will give it more grandeur and impressiveness. One of the unique features of the art of majestic sculpture is the depiction of artistic heroes in an upbeat spirit. Since majestic sculptures are intended to be viewed from a distance, large, solid forms are widely used in the depiction. Small elements on a person's face, folds in clothes, and small parts may not be shown.

Photo 2: Urganch city. Jalaluddin Manguberdi.

Figure 3: Tashkent city. Islam Karimov

Such statues are erected in order to commemorate historical events or the names of famous individuals. Majestic sculptures are designed to be seen from afar and are created in a generalized way in connection with the environment.

One of the special directions of majestic sculpture is majestic decorative sculpture. Works of this type, like magnificent sculptures, are intended for the general public, but they are more decorative.

There are easel, monumental, monument (memorial) decorative and monumental - decorative types of sculpture.

Majestic decorative sculptures are used to decorate streets and squares, buildings and parks, fountains. They depict people, animals, fish and birds. Since these statues are large in size, they can easily be seen from afar. The overall size, volume, and proportions of the magnificent works are adapted to the environment, nature, and buildings.

Figure 4: "Stella of Peace"
Namangan city 2007

**Figure 5: „Avesto“ symbolic monument
The city of Urganch in 2001**

*157- rasm Mustaqillik va ezgulik monumenti
Toshkent shahri (2005 y.)*

*158- rasm. Ibn Sino haykali
Latviya, Riga shahri, (2006 y.)*

South Dakota, USA. A national monument made of huge granite stone in honor of the four US presidents George Washington, Theodore Roosevelt, Thomas Jefferson and Abraham Lincoln. The total height of the monument is 122 meters. The width of each image face is 18 meters.

It was carved for 14 years by the famous sculptor Gatzon Borglum and his team of more than 400 people in 1927-1941.

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